

**A STUDY ON INFLUENCE OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON
CUSTOMER'S ONLINE BUYING BEHAVIOR (WITH
REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU)**

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Abstract:

The worldwide financial system in standard and worldwide exchange mainly have suffered and retain to go through massive losses from the covid-19. In the present research primary data were collected by structured questionnaire from 100 respondents in Coimbatore District. The main objectivity of the study was to analyse the factors influencing online buying behavior during Covid 19 pandemic in Coimbatore District. The collected data was analysed using simple percentage, Z test and ANOVA. The study concludes that COVID-19 pandemic issue may have an effect on large merchants, customers are experiencing a decrease in casual buying, deliver chain disruption, and expanded purchases of important hygiene and disinfection products, groceries, and other products.

Key Words: Customers, Hygine, Merchants, Covid 19, Buying, Satisfaction, Pandemic, Etc.,

Introduction:

The worldwide financial system in standard and worldwide exchange mainly have suffered and retain to go through massive losses from the covid-19. The uncertainty in which organizations and stop purchasers determined themselves immersed is further annoyed with the aid of more than one elements. The ones consist of profits decline, move-border travel regulations, shifting client demand, and the converting conduct of marketplace actors, to call a few. Global lockdown, social distancing, and different measures delivered to limit the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic have entreated customers to buy greater on the online marketplaces. The enterprise landscape faced speedy adjustments throughout the quarantine period as a result. Ultimately, the corona disaster elevated the improvement of virtual commerce. Globally, a brand new digitally immersed consumer has emerged, a more selective one, with monetary difficulties.

Income losses, restricted shipping opportunities, and pandemic mitigation measures, which induced the discount of supplier sports, have compelled B2B manufacturers and dealers to lessen manufacturing and marketing charges, locate new providers both abroad and within the us of a, and boost up decision making. Countrywide companies obtained opportunities to diversify their product portfolio for the purposes of import substitution and to deliver different companies and branches of overseas businesses with vital sources. B2C markets, then again, encountered a decline in purchasing power and cross-border mobility. On pinnacle of that, purchasers shifted towards fitness and protection at the same time as maintaining a preference for less expensive items and services. Merchandise that carry consolation and a experience of coziness to a residing area obtained more interest than they typically could. Standard, the uncertainty and unpredictability of the situation made customers delay a number of their demands. The commercial marketplace and purchaser market both faced a want to accelerate digitalization and make it easy to locate and purchase items online.

The pandemic sparked a meteoric rise in online income. As visits to physical stores had been constrained, and many were jogging low on money, consumers went online to shop, causing on-line purchases to grow better and higher . Customers had been typically mindful customers even earlier than the pandemic. Because of this, some purchasing categories which include reviews have been regularly downgraded on their priority lists, and COVID-19 accelerated matters on this route.

Purchaser behavior turned into motivated each by the COVID-19 pandemic itself and by using government restrictions. Purchasers of all generations throughout the COVID-19 disaster were much more likely to shop for items and offerings digitally. General, there has been a considerable shift toward e-commerce spending. The frequency of purchasing additionally elevated. Factors that force on-line consumer conduct all through the COVID-19 pandemic consist of sturdy and sustained growth in the quantity of net users and improved consciousness of on-line buying, an increasing number of lively online product releases, low charges because of bulk purchases, and many others.. The COVID-19 pandemic, social distancing, and staying at domestic are anticipated to push consumers to shop on-line. However, unsure patron demand and deliver chain issues could have an effect on the e-trade enterprise. The COVID-19 pandemic issue may have an effect on large merchants, who are experiencing a decrease in casual buying, deliver chain disruption, and expanded purchases of important hygiene and disinfection products, groceries, and other products.

Thinking about the changes in consumer conduct resulting from COVID-19, advertising research on this place has additionally undergone changes. Increasingly more advertising and marketing research on consumer behavior is taking place on line. Entrepreneurs needed to adapt fast and find innovative approaches to

engage with customers. Even though the state of affairs has been unpredictable, and selections are not continually smooth to make, the modern adjustments themselves cannot be known as essentially new. Actual-time analysis of changing customer behavior, integration of online and offline channels, automation, flexibility, and interest to network values have all been mentioned earlier than. The pandemic absolutely resulted in the accelerated scientific interest in these activities. Inside the new global, the role of on line analytics increases substantially: general quarantine is contemplated in consumer conduct. With out information what precisely has modified, businesses cannot plan their destiny actions. This is applicable to each marketing and income in standard. Whatever the global, the new types of research, strategies and technologies learned all through the pandemic are not temporary however are being confidently carried out and starting up a new space for coping with online patron behavior.

Review of Literature:

Prashant Singh (2014) examined that the main aim of the examine is to decide the purchaser’s buying behaviour towards online buying . The research discovered that destiny of e-outlets in India looking very bright. In latest days e-retailers deliver customers the best way to save money and time through shopping on line inside the range of cash. On this research main e-store additionally supplying a number of the satisfactory costs and absolutely problem-loose buying revel in. The research founded that whole idea of on-line shopping has altered in India in terms of patron’s purchasing or buying behavior.

Bharti Aggarwal Deepa Kapoor (2020) evaluated drivers of E-purchasing in the situation of COVID-19 pandemic and to decide the favored products that clients want to buy greater through online after COVID 19 pandemic. The examine is descriptive, in nature use of published reviews, use of posted studies papers in journals and current literature about this subject matter. The have a look at based that understanding the e- customers behavior below state of affairs of COVID-19 and this take a look at additionally assist the net shopping service providers to make higher strategies for supplying greater delight to clients and to win the opposition.

Shengyu Gu, Beata Slusarczyk, Sevda Hajizada, Irina Kovalyova and Amina Sakhbieva (2021), assessed the relationships and the extent of impact of the factors activating the shopping conduct of on-line consumers against the historical past of the COVID-19 pandemic. The have a look at changed into primarily based on the transformation of Cattell’s questionnaire and the implementation of correlation analysis. The survey became carried out among online shoppers within the pinnacle 10 nations in terms of e-buying marketplace boom. The study showed that changes in on line patron shopping for conduct are common within the COVID-19 pandemic. The impact of client consciousness and experience has improved. On line consumers have turn out to be extra experienced, which has stimulated the interest in their buying conduct. The findings of the study revealed that the transferring influence of online consumer purchasing behavior elements for the duration of the pandemic.

Objectives:

- To know the factors influencing customers online buying behavior during Covid 19.
- To analyse the customers level of satisfaction towards online buying behaviour during Covid 19 in Coimbatore District.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study is restricted to the selected sample of respondents in Coimbatore District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Research Methodology:

Area of Study: The research study was done in Coimbatore District.

Nature and Source of Data: The study is based on primary data; primary data has been collected from various respondents in Coimbatore District using questionnaire method and the secondary data have been collected from related websites, journals, magazines, internet and textbooks. A sample of 100 respondents were selected for the study.

Statistical Tools Used for Study:

- Simple percentage
- Z test
- Anova
- Friedman Ranking Test

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Personal Profile

Factors	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Gender		
Male	45	45

Female	55	55
Age		
Upto30	35	35
31 to 45	42	42
46 to 60	8	8
Above 60	15	15
Occupation		
Agriculture	23	23
Employee	37	37
Business	28	28
Others	12	12
Educational Qualification		
Up to school level	12	12
Under graduate/ Diploma	48	48
Post Graduate	24	24
Professional	16	16
Family Income per Month		
upto 25000	35	35
25001-40000	53	53
40001-60000	12	12

The profile of data collected from 100 Customers show that, 55 percent were female, 42 percent were in the age group of 31 to 45 years, 37 percent of the respondents were employed, 48 percent of the respondents were Under Graduates / Diploma and 53 percent of the respondent's monthly family income was between 25001-40,000.

Z – Test is used to study the opinion of the Customer on the basis of their gender.

Null Hypothesis: On an average both male and female have the same opinion on the factors influencing Customers satisfaction towards online shopping during covid 19

Table 2: Z test between Gender and factors influencing online buying behavior during Covid 19

Factor	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Z	Sig.
Social Distancing	Male	45	21.51	5.18	0.14	0.905
	Female	55	21.63	5.22		
Avoid crowd	Male	45	14.68	14.68	0.783	0.378
	Female	55	14.41	14.41		
Satisfaction to Buy	Male	45	19.73	3.03	0.130	0.719
	Female	55	19.96	3.30		
Avoid Covid 19 Risk	Male	45	28.40	6.92	2.288	0.134
	Female	55	26.34	6.62		

Table 2 reveals that, the calculated value are greater than 5% level of significance, hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that, on an average both male and female have the same opinion on the factors influencing online buying during Covid 19.

ANOVA is used to analyse the influence of demographic variables like age, education level and family monthly income on factors influencing online buying during Covid 19.

Table 3: ANOVA between Age and factors influencing online buying behaviour during Covid 19

Factor	Age	N	Mean	S.D	Z	Sig.
Social Distancing	upto20	70	21.62	5.73	0.712	0.598
	21to30	84	21.07	4.81		
	31to40	16	24.00	5.31		
	above40	30	21.60	4.85		
Avoid crowd	upto20	70	14.82	1.54	0.802	0.685
	21to30	84	14.42	1.46		
	31to40	16	13.75	1.98		
	above40	30	14.60	1.29		
Satisfaction to Buy	upto20	70	20.11	3.37	0.309	0.790
	21to30	84	19.73	3.31		
	31to40	16	19.00	2.82		
	above40	30	20.06	2.46		
Avoid Covid 19 Risk	upto20	70	28.37	8.42	0.326	0.001
	21to30	84	27.64	5.29		

	31to40	16	27.12	3.64		
	above40	30	23.73	7.01		

Table 3 indicates that, the calculated value are greater than 5% level of significance except in Avoid Covid 19 Risk, hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that, on an average different age group have the same opinion on the factors influencing online buying like Social Distancing, Avoid crowd and Satisfaction to Buy. The calculated value is lesser than 5% level of significance indicating that, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means on the average different age groups do not have the same opinion on Avoid Covid 19 Risk.

Table 4: ANOVA between education and Customers Satisfaction towards online buying behavior during Covid 19

Factor	Education	N	Mean	S.D	Z	Sig.
Social Distancing	school level	24	20.66	7.42	3.625	0.160
	graduate/diploma	96	22.41	4.81		
	Postgraduate	48	19.00	4.10		
	Professional	32	23.62	4.50		
Avoid crowd	school level	24	14.50	2.31	0.71	0.975
	graduate/diploma	96	14.50	1.27		
	Postgraduate	48	14.66	1.46		
	Professional	32	14.50	1.71		
Preference to buy	school level	24	21.25	2.63	1.533	0.211
	graduate/diploma	96	19.75	3.48		
	Postgraduate	48	20.12	2.49		
	Professional	32	18.75	3.19		
Avoid Covid 19 Risk	school level	24	22.50	6.73	2.943	3.370
	graduate/diploma	96	27.41	6.36		
	Postgraduate	48	27.62	4.95		
	Professional	32	29.87	9.03		

From the table 4 it is understood that, the calculated value are greater than 5% level of significance except in Avoid Covid 19 Risk, hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that, on an average different educational group have the same opinion on the Customers Satisfaction towards online buying during Covid 19 are Social Distancing, Avoid crowd and Preference to buy products

Table 5: ANOVA between family income and Customers Satisfaction towards online buying behavior during Covid 19

Factor	Family Income	N	Mean	S.D	Z	Sig.
Social Distancing	upto 15000	70	21.06	4.61	0.755	0.473
	15001-30000	118	22.42	6.08		
	30001-45000	12	21.66	4.92		
Avoid crowd	upto 15000	70	14.64	1.42	5.666	0.005
	15001-30000	118	14.62	1.41		
	30001-45000	12	13.00	2.36		
Preference to buy	upto 15000	70	20.69	3.16	5.78	0.007
	15001-30000	118	18.77	2.82		
	30001-45000	12	18.00	2.44		
Avoid Covid 19 Risk	upto 15000	70	26.11	6.66	0.950	0.390
	15001-30000	118	26.33	6.32		
	30001-45000	12	27.62	4.93		

The table 5 indicates that, the calculated value are greater than 5% level of significance except in Avoid Covid 19 Risk, hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred that, on an average different family income group have the same opinion on the Customer Satisfaction towards online buying during Covid 19 like Social Distancing, Avoid crowd and Preference to buy. The calculated value is lesser than 5% level of significance indicating that, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that Customers with different age groups do not have the same opinion on Avoid crowd and Preference to buy.

Conclusion:

The COVID-19 epidemic has modified normal social connections, our working, schooling, unfastened time spending and additionally buying geste. As referred to inside the Accenture exploration (2020), humans are dwelling else, shopping for else and, in severa methods, allowing else. As consumers acclimatize to residence counter blockade for a prolonged time frame, they're espousing no longer most effective new technology which grease paintings, look at, unfastened time conditioning but also consumption in a new and relevant way. On this exploration, we validate some of the several uncommon customer gets styles that got here to dominate the early

days of the change surge of the COVID-19 epidemic extremity within the surroundings of the India. The outcomes of the conducted exploration show that client get for the duration of purchasing inside the COVID-19 epidemic normally relies upon on fear-the lesser the worry, the lesser the alternate in shopping. As we expected, fears for health have been statistically good sized for the primary motives in selecting new particulars. The motives for the brand new purchase for our pattern of customers have been the high-quality, vacuity and convenience of the acquisition.

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